

MODELLING THE
EARTH'S
ATMOSPHERE

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The atmosphere is a complex and ever-changing system driven by immensely powerful forces. It redistributes heat energy at a prodigious rate — dwarfing, for instance, the total energy flow in all the world's electrical power distribution networks. These enormous energy flows in the atmosphere are in delicate balance with the input from the Sun, the exchange of heat with the oceans, and the loss of heat to interplanetary space.

Short-term fluctuations in this balance show themselves in the familiar day-to-day weather changes, with their complex, highly variable spatial patterns. Longer-term fluctuations mark what is usually called 'climate change', meaning changes on time scales from years to decades or longer. Intimately coupled with both weather and climate are subtle changes in the chemical composition of the atmosphere, some of them naturally occurring and some of them, to an ever-increasing extent, the result of human activity. The threat of possible global warming, and the thinning of the stratospheric ozone layer now being observed, imply a need to understand and predict the atmosphere far better than at present. Success will help the UK's long-term strategies in international environmental diplomacy, and making the most of the new economic opportunities that will arise from global change.

The Need For Better Models

At present we possess only a limited ability to predict long-term climatic and chemical change. One reason is the sheer complexity of the problem. It involves turbulent flow in the atmosphere and oceans on spatial scales from less than a millimetre to tens of thousands of kilometres, of which the changing patterns seen in views of the Earth from space give only a hint. It involves many other processes, physical, chemical and biological, that can interact with each other and with the movement of air and water in subtle and variable ways. Many of these processes and flow phenomena are as yet inadequately represented in computer models that attempt to simulate the climate system.

For instance it cannot yet be credibly predicted whether climate change will entail wetter or drier conditions for UK agriculture, over the coming decades. Nor can it be predicted whether there will be a change in the frequency and intensity of destructive storms. Such possibilities correspond to relatively small shifts in the natural patterns of energy flow. Improved models are essential in order to represent these shifts with sufficient accuracy.

Again, it cannot be predicted how far the stratospheric ozone depletion already observed in middle and high latitudes will develop, supposing, for instance, that international protocols on chemical emissions are adhered to. It is not known to what extent the whole climatic-chemical system is affected by external influences,

such as changes originating in the Sun. All these problems require improved models, and a better understanding of their limitations, before we can make more credible predictions of what will happen, and more credible estimates of the range of future possibilities.

Continuous and accurate measurements are also crucial for all these problems. The early exploitation of new observations in modelling is of primary importance.

Improved models are also needed to sharpen our knowledge of what has already happened. We cannot do controlled experiments on the atmosphere itself to test proposed explanations of what is observed. However, to an increasing extent, as super-computers become more powerful, we can do controlled experiments with models. This is becoming an important means of testing understanding. The models are becoming increasingly important, also, for interpreting and

extracting more information from disparate sources of observational data by what is known as 'data assimilation'. It appears certain that the best possible modelling capability will be seen as indispensable to an

advanced nation's ability to assess the current as well as the future state of our environment. On this will depend, in turn, the ability to assess the international regulatory requirements, the global security implications, and the economic opportunities that will follow.

The Challenge

Progress in developing better models of our climatic-chemical environment can come only from a sustained, multi-disciplinary research effort, which requires the recruitment of new scientific talent. We are faced with a major intellectual challenge worthy of our best mathematicians, physicists, chemists, biologists, and computer scientists. No matter how powerful computers become, and how adept we become at using them, it will never be possible to incorporate everything about the real atmosphere into the models. Nor can we incorporate everything about the influence of the Earth's land surface and oceans. The design of improved

models must go hand in hand with continual testing against observation, and continual attempts at improved understanding. This is because it will always be necessary to take account of which processes are most important, which ones can safely be omitted or simplified, and where the sensitive interdependences lie.

The UK Universities' Global Atmospheric Modelling Programme (UGAMP), whose work is described in this brochure, was initiated to help meet this challenge. UGAMP is a Community Research Project of the Natural Environment Research Council (NERC).

UV light splits oxygen molecules (O_2) into two single oxygen atoms

Free chlorine atoms released from CFC molecules react with ozone forming ClO and O_2

ClO is short lived, it reacts with a free O atom to form a further O_2 molecule, releasing the free Cl atom ready to decompose another ozone molecule

Schematic sequence of the destruction of ozone

Ozone In The

As part of its overall aim, UGAMP intends to perform the basic studies needed for developing a predictive capability for stratospheric ozone. Ozone is an extremely reactive gas, each molecule consisting of three oxygen atoms. It is found in trace quantities throughout the atmosphere, but mostly in the lower half of the stratosphere in the layer between about 10 and 30 kilometres altitude. It is created in some locations, transported by the winds and destroyed in others, at a total rate of the

ozone by Cl released from a CFC-12 molecule.

The Stratosphere

order of several million tonnes per day for the whole atmosphere. The total amount in the atmosphere at any one time is around several thousand million tonnes. This is far too large for direct artificial replenishment, but very small in global terms, representing, at most, about 10 molecules of ozone for every million molecules of other atmospheric gases. It is this small amount of ozone that shields us, and the rest of the marine and terrestrial biosphere, from life-damaging amounts of ultra-violet radiation.

Ozone—Climate Interactions

The ozone layer well illustrates the interaction between different physical and chemical processes. The replenishment rate of ozone, and its total amount, both depend on the climate and the associated global-scale air motion in all its complexity. By absorbing ultra-violet, and infra-red heat radiation also, ozone changes the heat balance of the atmosphere and so directly affects the climate and the air motion. These processes, in turn, all react back on the highly complex and delicate ozone chemistry, itself dependent on the ultra-violet radiation and on the interaction between many long-lived and short-lived chemical species, including man-made pollutants.

High-resolution numerical simulation of stratospheric motion. The different colours represent air masses with different chemical compositions. The dark blue central region corresponds to a possible polar ozone hole.

Polar And Mid-Latitude Ozone Depletion

The discovery of the Antarctic ozone hole by UK scientists in 1985, and the subsequent observation of more widespread ozone depletion in both hemispheres, has shown that ozone chemistry is even more complex than had previously been thought. There are additional chemical processes to consider, some of them associated with reactions on small haze or cloud particles in the stratosphere. The recent polar ozone measurement campaigns, and the eruption of Mount Pinatubo in June 1991, have provided timely opportunities to increase our observational knowledge of these processes. There are also interactions with turbulent fluid motions in the stratosphere that may be significant. Mixing takes place on time scales similar to the time scales of some of the important chemical reactions; no model of the ozone layer has yet correctly taken into account the simultaneous effects of chemistry and finite turbulent mixing time. Such effects may have a role in future mid-latitude ozone depletion, and pose one of the severest challenges for atmospheric modellers.

Only when the different air masses are brought very close together can mixing and the resulting chemical reactions take place. Conventional methods for computing such processes are notoriously inaccurate. The

results shown use a combination of supercomputer power and innovative numerical methods to achieve unprecedented accuracies. They will probably be used as a benchmark against which to test other, computationally cheaper methods, and the extent to which the modelling of ozone chemistry is affected.

Balloon-borne instruments probe the Antarctic atmosphere

MODELLING THE ATMOSPHERE

The UK Universities' Global Atmospheric Modelling Programme

WHY UK INVOLVEMENT?

Pressures on the environment from human activity are already producing clearly observable changes, globally as well as locally. Rates of change are expected to accelerate with the rise of world population (from 1 billion in mid-nineteenth century to the present 5 billion, and possibly to 14 billion next century); and the political and commercial implications will be far-reaching.

There are likely to be increasingly stringent national and international regulation of the management of natural resources and of all human activities that affect the environment. The cost of implementing these regulations could be high, but might be increasingly seen to be necessary.

UK atmospheric scientists have long

been intimately involved in advancing the scientific understanding necessary to frame international regulations. This involvement is important for its own sake but it is also of undoubted importance to both political and commercial decisions made in the UK as it has ensured an active scientific community whose expertise can be readily called upon.

NERC RESEARCH IN THE ATMOSPHERIC SCIENCES

The Natural Environment Research Council (NERC) shares responsibility for supporting UK research in the atmospheric sciences with the Science and Engineering Research Council (SERC) and the Meteorological Office, the latter in turn supported by the Ministry of Defence and the Department of the Environment (DoE). The Meteorological Office is largely concerned with improving weather forecasting and related operational services and, through its DoE-supported Hadley Centre for Climate Prediction and Research, with the development of operational climate forecasting. NERC and SERC support fundamental research into all areas of atmospheric science carried out by the university-based atmospheric sciences research community.

Research projects in these different parts of the community are complementary and cooperative, information being shared as a matter of course. Close relations are likewise maintained with the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts, which is based in the UK. The universities have a special role in recruiting and training young talent, in maintaining the wide-ranging inter-disciplinary expertise needed to understand global environmental change, and in encouraging long-term, high-risk research efforts capable of leading to radical advances.

The UK Universities' Global Atmospheric Modelling Programme (UGAMP) is helping to strengthen the role of the universities in UK atmospheric science, building on the UK's high international reputation in atmospheric modelling. This is in line with NERC's remit, described in *Air of Change*, the NERC Strategy for Atmospheric Sciences published in 1989, to focus on understanding the behaviour of the non-ionised regions of Earth's atmosphere, mostly below about 50 kilometres altitude, and to investigate the interactions between these regions and the Earth's land and ocean surfaces.

UGAMP was established in April 1990 as a Community Research Project of NERC's Marine and Atmospheric Science Directorate. Its approach is to use a hierarchy of models as research tools for controlled experimentation, for comparison with observational data, and in other ways for the advancement of basic understanding. It also aims to contribute to the improvement of models as understanding develops. The most sophisticated members of the hierarchy are high-resolution, three-dimensional, state-of-the-art models that attempt to simulate the global atmospheric circulation in as much detail as practicable. Other models lower in the hierarchy are used to focus on some processes in more detail, while leaving out others. The

overall aim is summarised in the 1991 UGAMP Science Plan as:

To improve our basic understanding of a variety of large-scale atmospheric phenomena and processes that are important in predictions of our climatic-chemical environment, thereby advancing the ability to simulate them correctly in models of the climate system.

An integral part of the project is to recruit and train tomorrow's researchers. Graduate students and postdoctoral researchers work alongside established and internationally respected scientists engaged in many different aspects of atmospheric modelling.

With its emphasis on the understanding that is necessary to produce the future models of greater predictive power, UGAMP is complementary with the Met Office/Hadley Centre effort whose focus is on prediction with the best available models. Indeed, each provides a stimulus for the activities of the other. The inter-disciplinary expertise on which it draws has been gradually built up over more than twenty years, in the research departments of universities and other institutions throughout the UK. This brochure describes the nature of the work being carried out by UGAMP, and highlights some of its achievements to date.

THE NATURE OF THE PROBLEM

Why are future long-term climatic-chemical changes in the atmosphere so hard to predict? There is the sheer complexity of the problem already mentioned. There is also a more fundamental reason. Almost all the physical and chemical processes involved have a property that mathematicians call 'nonlinearity'. This property can, and often does, lead to the strange and complex behaviour studied in 'chaos theory'. It can also lead to situations in which phenomena having very different space and time scales can affect each other surprisingly strongly. What this means in practice is that, in effect, one is adding to the well known difficulties of accurate day-to-day weather prediction — already a highly nonlinear problem — a range of extra difficulties associated with the far greater range of time scales and the far wider range of significant processes.

The point about disparate time scales is well illustrated by a phenomenon called the 'quasi-biennial oscillation', which also illustrates another fact noted in studies of chaos theory, the 'emergence of order from chaos'. Despite the generally chaotic behaviour exhibited by the atmosphere, a comparatively regular sequence of events has been observed in the equatorial lower stratosphere (altitudes 12 to 30 km) ever since observations began in the early 1950s. This sequence has nothing to do with the obvious external causes of regularity, the diurnal and annual variation in incident solar energy. It appears to involve a different set of time scales and to be purely a consequence of nonlinear dynamics internal to the atmosphere. Every thirteen to sixteen months — not twelve — the easterly winds in the equatorial lower stratosphere change to westerly winds, or vice versa, throughout a belt encircling the globe. The evolution consistently shows a characteristic space-time pattern with the wind reversals taking place earlier at higher altitudes. It is believed that a correct explanation of this phenomenon must involve several kinds of much faster processes, the fastest of which is tropical cumulonimbus convection. This latter involves a massive release of heat energy as water vapour condenses to form rain; turbulent fluid motions are generated on time scales of hours down to seconds. Also involved are certain large-scale wave

motions with time scales of days to weeks, coupled by the nonlinearities both to the cumulonimbus convection and to the slowly changing east-west winds in the stratosphere (Figure 1). The oscillation also impacts on the distribution of ozone over the entire globe.

The quasi-biennial oscillation happens to be one example of a phenomenon that no large atmospheric model has yet succeeded in simulating at all, let alone simulating accurately. 'Large' atmospheric model in this case means the type of three-dimensional mathematical model that attempts to be closest to the real atmosphere by including the most comprehensive range of interacting physical processes. Such models are called 'general circulation models'. On the other hand, by illustrating the 'emergence of order from chaos' in the real atmosphere, the existence of the quasi-biennial oscillation allows one to hope that, despite being a chaotic dynamical system, and despite the general impossibility of detailed weather forecasts over time scales of longer than two weeks, the atmosphere may be predictable, at least in some average respects, over much longer time scales. Studies of the quasi-biennial oscillation are one of UGAMP's priorities.

The point about disparate time scales

is even more strikingly illustrated by the observed behaviour of man-made chlorofluorocarbons (CFCs) in the atmosphere. These CFCs are the chemicals now known to be ultimately responsible for the Antarctic ozone hole and are widely believed to be responsible for global scale ozone depletion. It is known that it would take a time of the order of several centuries to get rid of most of the present atmospheric accumulation of CFCs. This is supposing that the leakage of these substances into the atmosphere could somehow be stopped immediately. In reality, it will take even longer. CFCs are chemically very inert and the only known destruction mechanism involves high energy ultraviolet radiation which is only present in the upper stratosphere (between 30 and 50 km) and above. The chlorine which is released from this destruction (and which is actually responsible for depleting ozone) is only finally removed when it returns to the lower atmosphere (the troposphere - below about 12 km). Thus the very long time scale is largely determined by the fact that there is a certain rate at which air from the troposphere recirculates through the stratosphere. The rate of circulation is in turn known to be largely determined by the average effects of fluid motions with time scales from days down to fractions of a second. The fact that these very slow and very fast time scales are so

Figure 1. A schematic illustration of some of the processes that are important in climate, showing the relatively turbulent troposphere in which weather occurs and the more stable stratosphere.

intimately connected is another of the characteristic consequences of nonlinearity.

Simulating such effects accurately is typical of the kind of challenge facing atmospheric modellers. It is typical of the reasons why understanding is needed as well as computer power. There is no way in which computer power alone will ever be enough to simulate in detail the full range of space and time scales involved in atmospheric motion. A combination of great computer power with great ingenuity and insight will be essential to success.

Another aspect of the problem is that very small amounts of gaseous pollutants — in dilutions as small as a few molecules per thousand million molecules of other atmospheric gases — can affect the atmosphere's energy balance to a surprising extent. This is partly because of the way in which the

different natural and man-made chemicals interact with each other, and with the Sun's radiation. In chemical language, 'catalytic cycles' are involved. This means for instance that one pollutant molecule can bring about the destruction of many thousands of molecules of ozone. Just how many, and under exactly what circumstances, is a typical question involving the full range of chemical, radiative, and fluid-dynamical processes— another high priority for UGAMP.

Many of these chemical substances interact with infra-red heat radiation in the same way as the main greenhouse gases; water vapour and carbon dioxide. This means that the same very small amounts of gaseous pollutants influence the infra-red radiation field, as well as the ultra-violet. They do this both directly and by chemically changing other gases, particularly

ozone. These differences can be enough to change the atmosphere's internal heat energy flows by amounts that correspond to significant changes in climate, and to change the ultra-violet radiation reaching the Earth's surface by amounts that can affect the biosphere.

The troposphere (Figure 1) contains about 80 percent of the mass of the atmosphere and extends on average to about 12 kilometres altitude. The middle atmosphere consists of the strato-sphere, from about 12 to 50 kilometres altitude, and the mesosphere above, reaching nearly to 100 kilometres and overlapping the ionosphere. The boundary between the troposphere and the stratosphere is called the tropopause, and the boundary between the stratosphere and the mesosphere is called the stratopause.

MODELLING THE ATMOSPHERE

UGAMP's Hierarchy of Models

Mathematical models of nonlinear dynamical systems like the atmosphere are, by their nature, expressed using 'nonlinear equations'. What this means in practice is that the equations usually need to be solved with the aid of a computer. Models that try to represent the atmosphere with any degree of realism call for large resources on large computers; and there is always a compromise between degree of realism, computational expense, how long a time the models can be run for, and how many model experiments can be performed. For the sake of flexibility — and also to help develop the required understanding of individual processes, as well as the interplay between them — UGAMP's approach is to use controlled experiments with a hierarchy of models of varying degrees of complexity, as research tools to further basic understanding. This entails testing cause-and-effect hypotheses, exploring the relative importance of different processes, and assessing the possible impact of perturbations to the climate system. Observational data are used both to suggest and to test hypotheses. Programmes for present and future research have been built on this approach, in which the models are used as experimental tools, somewhat

like laboratory experimentation in the traditional sciences.

The models of the hierarchy range from elaborate, state-of-the-art general circulation models to relatively simple models that deliberately focus on a more limited range of processes and are much cheaper to use. The models are all used for various stages of hypothesis-testing. They are also being used to assimilate observational data. One of UGAMP's recent successes has been the assimilation of observations of equatorial stratospheric east-west winds into a model of intermediate complexity, but sophisticated enough to be able to simulate the temperature, ozone and ultra-violet radiation changes associated with the quasi-biennial oscillation. This particular mode of data assimilation is simple, robust and trouble-free; but the combined use of model and data in this way turned out to be very effective. It has resulted in progress towards disentangling the relative roles of seasonal (annual) and quasi-biennial effects in the observed evolution of stratospheric ozone, a topic of great current interest in the international stratospheric-ozone community.

The UGAMP General Circulation Model

Most of the models used in UGAMP

have been developed within the UK university community over the last twenty years. The main exception is the UGAMP General Circulation Model (UGCM), a top-of-the-range model that tries to include a great number of the atmospheric processes involved in climate change. The UGCM has been adapted for long-range climate simulations, starting from the high-resolution weather forecasting model developed and used by the UK-based European Centre for Medium-range Weather Forecasts. This model is internationally respected as state-of-the-art. It is based on the now widely-used spectral modelling technique, which uses special functions to represent each model variable (for example temperature or wind velocity) as continuously varying in latitude and longitude, rather than as a series of values at discrete grid-points. This method, which the early UK university work helped to pioneer, has computational advantages over alternative methods based entirely on grid-point values. The further development of the UGCM by UGAMP so far includes increasing the vertical extent of the model to cover the middle atmosphere (stratosphere and mesosphere) as well as the troposphere (the extended UGCM, or EUGCM, see Figure 2).

Work is also under way to develop a hierarchy of 'chemistry modules' for

the UGCM. These attempt to represent the extremely complex sets of chemical equations needed to describe chemical reactions in the atmosphere, with varying degrees of sophistication. Runs of the UGCM incorporating a simple ozone chemistry model have already yielded realistic global ozone distributions and illustrated the movement of stratospheric ozone in sympathy with the underlying weather systems. A good general understanding of this interaction between ozone and weather was already available, but the ability to model it quantitatively is critical to the detailed interpretation of local ozone observations which are usually dominated by the weather-related variability. Such variability has to be accurately allowed for before deductions about chemical ozone depletion can be made. Other experiments have illuminated the role of atmospheric motions in providing a 'containment vessel' in which the recently discovered new chemistry responsible for ozone depletion above Antarctica can occur. These results have confirmed the promise of the UGCM as an excellent tool for middle atmosphere studies.

UGAMP is now using a version of the UGCM to examine the global movement of long-lived tracers in the atmosphere, such as the CFCs. These studies are important for many reasons, including, again, the interpretation of observations. It is possible that model studies like these will be useful for locating CFC sources and hence become important for the enforcement of international protocols on CFC emissions. Similar studies are

being used to trace the spread of volcanic debris through the stratosphere after the recent eruption of Mount Pinatubo in the Philippines. Such studies are of key importance for developing our understanding of the role of eddies and 'containment vessel' effects in the stratospheric ozone layer, and for the rates at which tropospheric material reaches various altitudes in the stratosphere, and vice versa — the so-called problem of 'stratosphere-troposphere exchange'.

At the time of writing the UGCM has

just been installed on the Research Councils' new and more powerful Gray Y-MP81/8128 supercomputer at the Rutherford Appleton Laboratory. The simpler models require less powerful computers such as the new generation of workstations. These workstations are also of crucial importance in analysing output from the UGCM and EUGCM. UGAMP is also fortunate in having access to the European Centre's database of global observations of atmospheric conditions, which is updated every six hours.

Figure 2. The January thermal structure of the atmosphere in terms of latitude and height as given by a UGAMP model which resolves the atmosphere up to about 90 Km. The warm regions are shown by light stippling and the cold by dense stippling. The regions of the atmosphere are indicated on the right and the pressure in millibars on the left.

KEY PROCESSES IN CLIMATE

Climate can be viewed as the distribution, intensity and frequency of occurrence of atmospheric phenomena collectively described as "weather". The phenomena can be viewed as the building bricks of climate. UGAMP is aiming to produce better understanding of a number of key phenomena and how their representation in predictive models can be improved. Confidence in predictions of climate change will be much higher if it is known that the present climate is predicted correctly in regional detail and not just in the global averages.

Tropical Cumulonimbus Convection and its Wider Implications

One of the most demanding problems in atmospheric modelling is how, using available computers, to take account of powerful processes whose scale is too small to be described in a global model. A deep cumulonimbus cloud (the type of cloud often associated with thunder storms) may seem to the human observer to be an awesomely large-scale phenomenon; but it is a mere pinprick when viewed on the global or even regional scale. Yet it is essential to represent in global models

the statistical effects of large numbers of cumulonimbus clouds and similar 'convective cloud' phenomena. They are of prime importance to the global scale flow of energy.

UGAMP has carried out the first major tests, in long-time integrations of the UGCM, of a new way of modelling the collective effects of tropical cumulonimbus clouds, demonstrating a major impact on the large-scale circulation and tropical variability (Figure 3).

Tropical cumulonimbus clouds often occur in definite regions associated with larger scale weather systems. For

example much of the rainfall in the huge region of the west Pacific, which is important to the whole climate system, is observed to be associated with weather systems whose size is more than 1000 km and which recur, typically, every four days. UGAMP research has shown that different ways of representing the effects of the cumulonimbus clouds lead to totally different behaviour of the modelled large scale systems.

On even larger scales there is often a large variation in tropical cumulonimbus clouds and wind patterns on a time scale of one to two months. Currently models are unable to capture this phenomenon and UGAMP is attempting to see why by using observed data, a range of simple models and the UGCM with different representations of the effects of cumulonimbus clouds. Already new results have been obtained on the way this one to two month variation affects not just the tropics but also a lot of the Earth.

Mid-Latitude Cyclones and "Storm Tracks"

The UK's climate and rainfall, both in winter and in summer, depend sensitively on the flows of heat energy

and water vapour associated with mid-latitude cyclones (or depressions) originating off the eastern seaboard of North America. These travel across the Atlantic Ocean, amplifying as they go. Their average path, or 'storm track', varies from month to month and from year to year. This is a major factor in local climate change. In some winters, a succession of cyclones cause severe rainfall and gale-force winds over the UK and Western Europe; in others, the storm track diverts away from the UK, leaving the country to experience a more continental-type winter climate, often accompanied by poor air quality as pollution stagnates in slow-moving anticyclonic weather systems. The reasons for such changes are not yet fully understood, although model experiments carried out under UGAMP have pointed towards some of the likely causes.

UGAMP research has shown the great sensitivity of the growth and decay of cyclonic storms to details in the flow in which they develop and to representations of cumulonimbus clouds and other small scale processes. More research is needed in this area because current forecast models make important errors in the pattern of mid-latitude cyclones when forecast more than a few days ahead and climate

models generally have significant errors in their cyclonic storm statistics.

Periodicity and Organisation in Climate Change

Although it is well known that climate changes can occur on long as well as short time-scales, it is not known to what extent this periodicity is the result of external forces, such as changes in the Sun's radiation or in the atmospheric composition, or of internal dynamical interactions within the atmosphere. UGAMP therefore set up an experiment in which a numerical simulation of climate change over a period of 200 years was carried out using a simplified global model of the atmosphere, in which only the third factor could operate (internal dynamical interactions within the atmosphere). Analysis of the time variation of one indicator of the atmospheric circulation, the strength of the mid-latitude zonal wind, revealed that it contained surprisingly long time scales. This strongly suggests that observed long-period climate variability can be attributed, at least partially, to processes internal to the atmosphere, not necessarily involving any of the external influences mentioned above.

Figure 3. The variability of the heat lost to space (Wm^{-2}) in two runs of the UGAMP model which are identical apart from their representation of cumulo-nimbus and shallow convection. The run with the new scheme is below.

STRATOSPHERE-TROPOSPHERE EXCHANGE

The remarkably long lifetimes of the CFCs in the atmosphere are largely determined by the fact that there is a certain rate at which air from the troposphere recirculates through the stratosphere (Figure 1). More precisely, there is a certain rate at which the air recirculates through those parts of the stratosphere that are reached by solar ultra-violet radiation of sufficiently high energy to decompose CFCs. Many other chemical constituents are affected by ultra-violet in a similar way, and so their chemistry likewise depends on recirculation rates through various altitude ranges, depending on how energetic the ultra-violet needs to be in order to have its effect. Conversely, the rate of supply of ozone and other photochemical products from the stratosphere to the troposphere strongly depends on recirculation rates, in a similar way.

It has also been mentioned that the rate of circulation is, in turn, largely determined by the average effects of fluid motions with time scales from days down to fractions of a second. The most important such motions can be thought of as particular kinds of waves. These waves propagate up from the troposphere into the stratosphere and, very often, undergo a breakdown to turbulent motion somewhere in the stratosphere. The picture on the back cover shows a high-resolution simulation of a breaking wave whose dynamics depends on the fact that the Earth and the atmosphere are rotating.

The combined effects of these wave motions, and the turbulent motions they induce, bear a close analogy to those of ocean waves breaking on a beach, producing the turbulent, foamy water that we call 'surf'. In the case of the stratosphere there are two important consequences. First, it turns out that the rate of recirculation of trace chemicals is related to the rate at which the waves arrive and break, or otherwise dissipate. Second, the turbulent air motion produced by the wave breaking can mix chemicals together, and thus change the chemical evolution from what it would otherwise be. Models have hardly begun to take this process correctly into account, partly because of the very high horizontal resolution required. The back cover picture gives some idea of the problem.

The detailed manner in which tropospheric air enters the stratosphere, and vice versa (Figure 1), is also of interest, and very much a topic of current research interest. Tropospheric air enters the stratosphere mainly in the tropics, in ways that are closely connected with cumulonimbus convection, but not understood in detail. Stratospheric air enters the troposphere mainly in middle and high latitudes, some or all of it (it is not yet known which) via intriguing structures called tropopause folds, part of the weather-front structures found in middle-latitude cyclones. Versions of the UGCM with high horizontal resolution are just beginning to be capable of resolving these structures (see figure 4). The new Y-MP8I/8128 supercomputer will enable exciting progress to be made in describing tropopause folds and their role in stratosphere-troposphere exchange.

Stratospheric Ozone Depletion

UGAMP is seeking to understand the present chemical state of the stratosphere and mesosphere and its interaction with radiation and dynamics, including the ozone losses that have occurred over the last ten years. This means that it must confront the many issues and model the processes already discussed. For example, the different natures of the chemical containment by the northern and southern wintertime polar vortices, the crucial role played by small-scale and large-scale waves in the middle atmosphere, the formation and

effects of polar stratospheric clouds, the effects of aerosols, the transport of trace chemicals, the representation of chemistry occurring on the molecular scales and the quasi-biennial oscillation are all important. The natural variability of stratospheric ozone must also be investigated so that the importance of the observed changes in the last decade can be assessed.

Of great importance in this work will be the ready availability of data from the current NASA Upper Atmosphere Research Satellite (UARS). UGAMP Project Scientists have close involvement with two particular instruments on UARS. The European Arctic Stratospheric Ozone Experiment (EASOE) of the winter 1991-92 was led by a UGAMP scientist. The detailed measurements made in EASOE are being used to initialise and test UGAMP models. The roles of aerosols originating from the Mount Pinatubo eruption and the very unusual high pressure cell which was centred over the UK in the winter of 1991-92, need to be disentangled from the more general processes relevant to ozone depletion.

Figure 4. A simulation of a tropopause folding event in which stratospheric air, characterised by its low humidity descends into the lower troposphere. This was obtained using the high resolution UGAMP GCM.

SOME UGAMP SCIENTIFIC 'FIRSTS'

Long-time model integrations at unprecedentedly high resolution, demonstrating significant impact even for gross features of the circulation.

A clear demonstration that some of the global atmospheric variability on time scales as long as 10 years can arise purely from the fluid dynamics of the atmosphere, and need not depend on external influences or coupling to slower-evolving systems such as the oceans.

First major tests, in long-time integrations of a climate general circulation model, of a new way of modelling the collective effects of tropical cumulonimbus convection, demonstrating a major impact on the large-scale circulation and tropical variability.

Progress towards disentangling seasonal from quasi-biennial effects on stratospheric ozone.

First high-resolution simulations of three-dimensional stratospheric Rossby-wave breaking and polar vortex behaviour (see back cover).

Progress toward better ways of modelling chemical transport, including fundamentally new approaches.

Use of a large model to simulate short-term chemical transport in enough detail to permit direct comparison with local observations. This is setting new standards in testing model chemistry directly against observation, and has increased the value of data obtained, for instance, during the recent European Arctic Stratospheric Ozone Experiment.

THE UGAMP STRUCTURE

UGAMP is a Community Research Project of the Marine and Atmospheric Science (MAS) Directorate of NERC. The Director MAS is advised on UGAMP by a Scientific Steering Group.

The current 12 UGAMP Project Scientists come from seven departments in six universities: Cambridge, East Anglia, Edinburgh, London (Imperial College), Oxford and Reading, as well as the Rutherford Appleton Laboratory.

To provide the necessary infrastructure and support to the UGAMP community, in 1992 NERC is setting up the Centre for Global Atmospheric Modelling (CGAM) in the Department of Meteorology at the University of Reading, and the Atmospheric Chemistry Modelling Support Unit (ACMSU) in the Centre of Atmospheric Science at the University of Cambridge. The Director of CGAM will also be Scientific Director of UGAMP.

UGAMP presently funds 4 coordinator positions, a number of central unit staff and a number of research topic staff. Considerable funding for additional UGAMP-related staff comes mainly from NERC, the Science and Engineering Research Council, the European Community and the Department of the Environment. The coordinators, as well as taking a leading scientific role, coordinate the efforts in certain modelling areas across the UGAMP community.

ADDRESSES

There are UGAMP research groups working at the centres given below. Further information may be obtained from the Director of UGAMP or the NERC Programme Director for Atmospheric Sciences.

Programme Director for Atmospheric Sciences

Marine and Atmospheric Sciences Directorate
Natural Environment Research Council
Polaris House
North Star Avenue
Swindon SN2 1EU
Fax: 0793 411545

Space Science Department

Rutherford Appleton Laboratory
Space Science Department
Chilton, Didcot
Oxon OX11 0QX
Fax: 0235 445848

Department of Meteorology

University of Reading
2 Earley Gate
Whiteknights, PO Box 239
Reading RG6 2AU
Fax: 0734 352604

School of Environmental Science

University of East Anglia
Norwich, NR4 7TJ
Fax: 0603 507719

Director of UGAMP Centre for Global Atmospheric Modelling

Harry Pitt Building
3 Earley Gate
Whiteknights
PO Box 238
Reading RG6 2BZ
Tel: 0734 318317
Fax: 0734 318316

Centre for Atmospheric Science

Department of Applied Mathematics
and Theoretical Physics
University of Cambridge
Silver Street
Cambridge CB3 9EW
Fax: 0223 337918

Department of Meteorology

James Clerk Maxwell Building
The King's Buildings
University of Edinburgh
Mayfield Road
Edinburgh EH9 3JZ
Fax: 031662 4269

Atmospheric Chemistry Modelling Support Unit

Centre for Atmospheric Science
Department of Chemistry
University of Cambridge
Lensfield Road
Cambridge CB2 1EP
Fax: 0223 467390

Space and Atmospheric Physics Group

The Blackett Laboratory
Imperial College of Science and
Technology and Medicine
London SW7 2BZ
Fax: 071823 8250

Department of Atmospheric, Ocean and Planetary Physics

University of Oxford
Clarendon Laboratory
Parks Road
Oxford OX1 3PU
Fax: 0865 272923

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MODELLING THE ATMOSPHERE

Left: Total ozone in the atmosphere on a particular day simulated by the UGAMP model.

Below: Height time-series of quasi-biennial oscillation (QBO) in temperature (degrees K) simulated by a 2-dimensional model in which the effects of Kelvin and Rossby Gravity waves have been parameterised.

Modelled Temperature QBO at Equator (degrees K)

The average daily rainfall associated with cumulonimbus clouds in January simulated by a UGAMP model. The colour bar gives the amounts in mm per day.

A high-resolution, three-dimensional simulation of the winter-time stratosphere. The colours mark the different air masses at an altitude of about 30km. Using Workstations UGAMP scientists can study the detail along a line such as that shown. Current observing systems are unable to observe such fine structure.